

The Effect of Silane Coupling Agents with Different Organofunctional Groups on the Interfacial Characteristics of Glass Fiber-Reinforced Nylon 6 Composites: Microscopic and Macroscopic Approaches

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SUMMARY: In this study, the effect of silane coupling agents with different organofunctional groups on the interfacial characteristics of glass fiber-reinforced Nylon 6 composites has been investigated by means of single fiber microbonding test, short-beam shear test, dynamic mechanical analysis, scanning electron microscopy and thermogravimetric analysis. The results show that the fiber-matrix interfacial characteristics obtained from both microscopic and macroscopic approaches agree well each other. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of glass fiber/Nylon 6 composites sized with various silane coupling agents are significantly improved in comparison with those of the composite sized commercially. The interfacial properties of the composites increase in order of Z-6076 with chloropropyl groups, Z-6030 with methacrylate groups, Z-6040 with epoxide groups, and Z-6020 with diamine groups in the silanes. The dynamic mechanical properties, the fracture surface observations and the thermal stability also support the interfacial results. The improvement of the interfacial and dynamic mechanical properties may be ascribed to different chemical reactivities between the reactive amino end groups at Nylon 6 and the organofunctional groups located at the end of silane chains, resulting from the increased chemical reactivity in order of chloropropyl > methacrylate \approx epoxide > diamine groups.

KEYWORDS: fiber-matrix adhesion, silanes, sizing interphase, single fiber microbonding, interfacial and interlaminar shear strengths, dynamic mechanical property

INTRODUCTION

An introduction of interphase by use of coupling or sizing agents to a fiber-reinforced polymer composite material not only provides the ability to control the interfacial characteristics at the interface between the fiber and the matrix in a composite, depending on the chemical and physical interaction involved, but also contributes to improving various properties of a composite material [1-2].

The chemical bonding at the fiber-matrix interfaces is critically important to understand the interfacial strength in a fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite. Especially, an application of silane-based sizing interphase onto glass fiber surface not only protects the fiber from possible surface damages on handling, but also significantly improve the adhesion between the

reinforcing fibers and thermosetting or thermoplastic polymer matrix [2-6]. The chemical bonds can be formed between the chemical groups at the fiber surface and in the polymer matrix resin. For instance, the hydroxyl groups in the silanols [Si(CH₃O)] of a silane coupling agent and the hydroxyl groups at the glass fiber surface can form the chemical bonds. The organo-functional groups located at the end of silane chains with the other end anchored at the glass fiber surface may form the chemical bonds with reactive amino end groups in the Nylon 6 molecular chains. Silane compounds with different organo-functional groups may importantly influence the chemical reactivity and the bonding strength between inorganic glass fiber and organic polymer resin [3].

The experimental approaches for examining the interfacial properties between reinforcing fiber and matrix are largely divided into two categories. The one is to use a simplified fiber-matrix specimen for the interfacial measurement of a composite material. The typical examples are single fiber pull-out test, single fiber microbonding test and embedded single fiber fragmentation test [7-8]. These methods use a model composite composed of a single filament fiber as representative reinforcing fiber and of a thermoplastic or thermosetting resin as representative matrix to mimic the practical composite material with corresponding fibers and matrix. The test results may provide useful information on predicting the interfacial property of a composite. The other is to directly use a real composite specimen in the interfacial measurement. The typical examples are short-beam shear test [9], microindentation test [9], fracture toughness test [10] and dynamic mechanical analysis [11,12]. These methods are also widely used because they may provide practical information on the interfacial properties of a real composite material. All the methods above-mentioned may give quantitative information. Also, qualitative interpretation on the interfacial phenomenon may be obtained from microscopic observations of the fiber-matrix fracture surfaces of a composite.

Consequently, the objective of the study is to microscopically and macroscopically investigate the effect of various silane coupling agents with different organo-functional groups on the interfacial and dynamic mechanical properties of glass fiber-reinforced Nylon 6 composites through a single fiber microbonding test, short-beam shear test, dynamic mechanical analysis, and fracture surface observations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. Continuous E-glass fiber filaments (RS2200KT-111A, Owens Corning, U.S.A.) and E-glass woven fabrics with plain texture (KN 1800-HS, Kangnam Chemical Co., Korea) were independently used as reinforcing fibers in this work. The average diameter of a continuous single fiber filament is about 16 μm . The ‘as-received’ fiber surface is commercially sized but the information has not been released from the manufacturer. The thickness per ply of the ‘as-received’ fabric is 0.18mm \pm 0.02 mm. Pellet type Nylon 6 resin (Grade MC100L), supplied in the pellet form from Kanebo Gohsen, Ltd., Japan, was used as matrix resin. Glass fibers, glass fabrics and Nylon 6 were sufficiently dried in an oven prior to fabrication of each composite specimen.

Four silane coupling agents with different organo-functional groups, supplied from Dow

Corning Corp. U.S.A., were used to explore their effects on the interfacial characteristics of glass fiber/Nylon 6 composites. The commercial sizes on the glass fiber surface were completely desized at 400°C for 45 min prior to sizing treatment in the present study. The sizing content of 1.0 wt% has been used throughout this work. Table 1 summarizes the chemical structure and name of silane-based coupling agents with different organo-functional groups used.

No	Trade Name*	Chemical Name Chemical Structure	Organofunctional Group
1	Z-6020	N-2-Aminoethyl-3-aminopropyl trimethoxysilane $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Si}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$	Diamine
2	Z-6030	3-Methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane $\text{CH}_2=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COO}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Si}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$	Methacrylate
3	Z-6040	3-Glycidoxylpropyltrimethoxysilane $\text{OCH}_2\text{CHCH}_2\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Si}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$	Epoxy
4	Z-6076	3-Chloropropyltrimethoxysilane $\text{Cl}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Si}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$	Chloropropyl

Glass fiber-Nylon 6 Microdroplet Formation. In general, it is not easy to successfully form a microdroplet of thermoplastic resin on a single filament of glass fiber of 16 μm in diameter in case that the resin is highly crystallizable upon cooling subsequently after melting like polyamides. The size of the microdroplet is critically important for successful debonding between the single filament and the resin microdroplet under given loads during the microbonding test. The following statement describes in detail how to successfully form a thermoplastic Nylon 6 microdroplet on a single filament of glass fiber.

1. Place and heat a single pellet of Nylon 6 on a hot plate set to be melted.
2. Manually spin a single filament of Nylon 6 to be very fine by carefully pulling out the melted pellet.
3. Place the spun single filament of Nylon 6 to be perpendicularly across with a single filament of glass fiber on the hot plate.
4. Lift up the glass filament as soon as the Nylon 6 filament is remelted. On this occasion, a very tiny amount of the Nylon 6 resin will cover the fiber surface as a microdroplet.
5. Remelt the resin near the melting point revolving on the glass fiber axis at both ends to make the resin microdroplet uniform.
6. Cool down the microdroplet uniformly formed around the fiber.
7. Determine a proper size and shape of the microdroplet for optimal measurements through optical microscopic observations and preliminary microbonding test. The average diameter of the round-shape microdroplet made in this work is about 120 μm.

Fabrication of Glass Fiber/Nylon 6 Composites. Glass fiber/Nylon 6 composites were fabricated in a compressive molding machine using a film stacking method. A number of Nylon 6 films were prepared repetitively by melting at 228°C for 30 seconds and then naturally cooling in between two clean and smooth stainless steel plates using a hot press. The Nylon 6 films interleaved between the glass fabrics were sufficiently impregnated and consolidated under given melting and cooling cycles. The applied pressure was 1000 psi during processing. A number of glass fabrics and Nylon 6 films were stacked alternately in a steel mold. The composites were fabricated by melting at 228°C for 5 min, pressing at 1000 psi for 1.5 min, and then naturally cooling down to the ambient temperature. The dimensions of the composite fabricated were 50 mm × 50 mm. The thickness of each composite specimen was prepared

according to individual test requirements. The average thickness per ply in a composite is about 0.32 mm. The ratio of the resin to the fiber in the composite is 6:4.

Analysis. A thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA 951, TA Instrument) was used to examine the content of the commercial size of ‘as-received’ glass fibers and the thermal stability of the fibers and the composites. A heating rate of 10°C/min was used purging a N₂ gas of 50 cc/min.

The single fiber microbonding test was performed using a universal testing machine (UTM: Instron 4467). The distance between the resin microdroplet and the grip was 20 mm. No slippage at the filament end glued on a stiff paperboard was observed during the test. A crosshead speed of 5 mm/min was used throughout the test. 12~15 specimens were used for each measurement and the measured values were averaged.

The short-beam shear tests of the composites were conducted according to ASTM D-2344 using a UTM (Instron 4467). The crosshead speed was 1.3 mm/min and the span-to-depth ratio was 5. Ten specimens were used for each measurement.

The storage modulus, loss modulus and tan δ of the composites were measured in the vertical mode using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA 983, TA Instrument). The heating rate of 2°C/min was used with purging a N₂ gas of 50 cc/min. Use of the slow rate is to minimize the possible thermal lag between the program temperature and the composite specimen temperature. A fixed frequency of 1 Hz and the oscillation amplitude of 0.25 mm were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present work, TGA thermograms for commercially sized and desized glass fibers were studied to examine the sizing content in the ‘as-received’ fiber. The result informed that the commercial size starts to lose its weight around 150°C and is completely removed below 400°C due to decomposition. The content of the commercial size is estimated to be approximately 1 % of the total fiber weight used. This provides useful information to determine the content of silane coupling agents to be sized in the present study. It has been found from microscopic observations that sizing of 1 wt% does not alter significantly the appearance of the surface. The thickness is expected to be less than 0.1 μm. It is noted that the surface chemistry of glass fiber may be changed due to different interactions between the hydroxyl groups in the fiber surface and the hydroxyl groups of silanols in the silane coupling agents having different organo-functional groups onto the fiber surface, although the appearance of the surface does not change significantly.

Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS). Fig. 1 shows a schematic illustration of a single fiber microbonding test and optical microphotographs showing a Nylon 6 microdroplet formed around a glass fiber filament before and after the microbonding test. As can be seen, the original shape of the microdroplet was maintained even after the microbonding test. The applied load resulting in debonding shifts the original location of the microdroplet.

Fig. 2 compares the interfacial shear strengths obtained for glass fiber/Nylon 6 composites

Fig. 1. (A) Schematic illustration of a single fiber microbonding test and (B) optical microphotographs showing a Nylon 6 microdroplet formed on a single glass fiber filament before (left) and after (right) the microbonding test (Z-6076 sized).

sized with four silane coupling agents having different organo-functional groups at the end of the molecule using a microbonding test method. The result is also compared with the composite counterpart sized commercially. The IFSS values were calculated according to the following equation.

$$\tau = F/(\pi \cdot D_f \cdot L_e)$$

where τ is the IFSS, F is the force required for debonding the Nylon 6 microdroplet from the single glass fiber filament while tensile loads are applied, D_f is the diameter of the measuring fiber including the microdroplet, and L_e is the fiber length embedded in the Nylon 6 microdroplet.

As shown in Fig. 2, use of silane coupling agents significantly improves the IFSS of E-glass fiber/Nylon 6 composite in comparison with the counterpart sized commercially. Such the improvement indicates that the adhesion at the interfaces between the fiber and the resin is largely increased. Especially, it has been found that the composite sized with the silane coupling agent (Z-6076) having chloropropyl organo-functional groups at the molecular ends shows the highest IFSS. The interfacial strength is enhanced by approximately 140 % in comparison with that of the commercially sized one. On the other hand, the composite sized with the Z-6020, which has diamine groups in the silane molecule, shows the lowest improvement of the interfacial property. The IFSS is increased by approximately 37 %. Also, the composites sized with the Z-6030 having methacrylate groups and with the Z-6040 having epoxide groups as organo-functional groups exhibit a large increase of the interfacial strength by 132 % and 115 %, respectively.

Fig. 2. IFSS for various silane-sized glass/Nylon 6 composites by microbonding tests.

Fig. 3. ILSS for various silane-sized glass/Nylon 6 composites by short beam shear tests.

Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS). Fig. 3 compares the interlaminar shear strengths for glass/Nylon 6 composites sized with four silane coupling agents, as depicted in Fig. 3. The short-beam shear testing was done with removing the applied load as soon as the initial delamination between the fiber and matrix takes place through the thickness in a composite right after the yield point. The averaged ILSS values were obtained from the maximum load of the stress-strain curve for each specimen using the following equation.

$$\tau_{\max} = 3P_{\max}/4b \cdot t$$

where τ_{\max} is the ILSS, P_{\max} is the maximum load, b is the width of the specimen, and t is the thickness of the specimen.

Similarly with the IFSS result in Fig. 3, the ILSS value is the greatest with the Z-6076 that has chloropropyl organo-functional groups at the molecular ends. Comparing with the commercially sized composite, the ILSS is remarkably improved by 196%. In addition, the ILSS in the Z-6030 is significantly increased by 82%. It is also slightly increased by 6% in the case of the Z-6020. Even though the improvement in the ILSS is relatively lower than that in the IFSS, the tendency of the improvement is more or less comparable with each other, with the exception of the Z-6040. The ILSS value of the Z-6040 is even lower than that of the commercially sized one. The reason for this discrepancy has been found from some possible causes occurred during the composite fabrication. There has been no wetting problem with the formation of the Nylon 6 microdroplet on a single fiber filament in the all the specimen for microbonding tests. However, in the glass/Nylon 6 laminate prepared using the Z-6040 coupling agent only, it was found that the glass fiber surface is not sufficiently wetted or impregnated by the Nylon 6 resin under the identical processing condition for fabricating other composites. Such the poor wetting is because the Z-6040 of relatively high viscosity puts the fiber filaments together. The resin cannot be properly impregnated into the individual filaments bound together, causing the incomplete fabrication of the composite with pores. Such the wetting problem may weaken the interlaminar strength between the fiber and the matrix and result in the lowest value of ILSS. Therefore, the result suggests that the Z-6040 is not appropriate for applying on the fiber surface to make a glass/Nylon 6 composite although it increases the IFSS value obtained by the microbonding test.

Fig. 4 shows the scanning electron microphotographs observed in the delaminated region after the short-beam shear test for various glass fabric/Nylon 6 composites sized with different coupling agents. The result indicates that the strongest adhesion between the fiber and the matrix is seen in Fig. 4E (Z-6070) and the poorest adhesion is in Fig. 4D (Z-6040). It is likely that the composite in Fig. 4C has the better adhesion than the composites in Figs. 4A and 4B. These microscopic views also support the result of short-beam shear test.

Fracture Surface. Fig. 5 represents the scanning electron microphotographs showing the fracture surfaces of Nylon 6 composites reinforced with glass fabrics desized and sized with various coupling agents. The result indicates that the glass/Nylon 6 composite (F) sized with the Z-6070 exhibits the highest adhesion between the fiber and the matrix resulting in the greatest extent of the resin adhering on the pulled-out fiber surface upon fracture, reflecting a ductile fracture pattern. As expected, Fig. 5E microscopically demonstrates that use of the Z-6040

Fig. 4. Scanning electron microphotographs (1000×) in the delaminated region after the short-beam shear test for various glass fabric/Nylon 6 composites sized with different coupling agents. A: commercially sized, B: Z-6020, C: Z-6030, D: Z-6040, E: Z-6076.

Fig. 5. Scanning electron microphotographs showing the fracture surfaces of Nylon 6 composites reinforced with various glass fabrics (A) commercially sized, (B) desized, (C) Z-6020, (D) Z-6030, (E) Z-6040, and (F) Z-6076. The scale bar indicates 10μm at magnification of 1000×.

decreases the fiber-matrix adhesion in the glass/Nylon 6 composite, leaving a number of traces of clearly pulled-out fibers behind. It is also observed that there is a greater extent of the resin remaining on the fiber surface after fracture in Figs. 5C and 5D, compared with the commercially sized counterpart in Fig. 5A. The composite fabricated with desized glass fabrics in Fig. 5B shows the most clearly pulled-out fibers without the remaining resin after fracture, reflecting the very poor adhesion between the fiber and the matrix.

Dynamic Mechanical Behavior. Figs. 6 and 7 represent the dynamic mechanical behavior of glass/Nylon 6 composites fabricated using glass fabrics sized with four different silane coupling agents and also sized commercially for comparison. Fig. 6 depicts the variation of the storage modulus as a function of temperature. The storage modulus of the composites sized with Z-6030 and Z-6076 is slightly greater than that of the commercially sized counterpart. The composite sized with Z-6020 exhibits the comparable log E' with the commercially sized one. However, the modulus of the composite sized with Z-6040 is the lowest. This dynamic mechanical result is quite consistent with the ILSS result. The lowest storage modulus for Z-6040 is attributed to the poor adhesion between the fiber and the matrix as described earlier. The glass transition temperature (T_g) in a fiber reinforced polymer composite, in general, increases with increasing the interfacial strength between the fiber and the matrix. The T_g can be normally determined from the maximum peak temperature of a tan δ curve. Fig. 7 shows the variation of the tan δ as a function of temperature for the composites. It is expected that the T_g of Nylon 6 is significantly enhanced by an incorporation of reinforcing glass fibers. The T_g of the glass/Nylon 6 composites sized with the silane coupling agents used in this work is increased by 4~8°C in comparison with the commercially sized one, except for the case of Z-6040. The reason for the lowest value of T_g is found from the explanation described earlier.

Thermal Stability. Fig. 8 compares the thermal stability of the glass/Nylon 6 composites studied. All the composite specimens degrade beyond 350°C, showing a dramatic weight loss, which is responsible for the Nylon 6 resin. The composite sized with the Z-6076 exhibits the highest thermal stability. The result also indicates that the composites sized with the silane

Fig. 6. Variations of the storage modulus as a function of temperature for Nylon 6 composites reinforced with glass fabrics sized with different silane coupling agents.

Fig. 7. Variations of the tan δ as a function of temperature for the glass/Nylon 6 composites

coupling agents used here have slightly improved thermal stability in the temperature range prior to degradation. This is due to the increased interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the matrix in the composites, which may somewhat contribute to slightly deactivating and retarding the thermal degradation.

Fig. 9 illustrates proposed reaction schemes between the different organo-functional groups in the silane coupling agents and the amino groups in the Nylon 6 resin occurring during the composite fabrication. The chemical reactivity between the organo-functional groups located at the end of silane coupling agents with the other end anchored at the glass fiber surface and the reactive amino end groups of Nylon 6 resin differs. The possibility of the chemical bond formation between the silane coupling agent and the Nylon 6 increases with increasing the chemical reactivity in order of chloropropyl > methacrylate \approx epoxide > diamine organofunctional groups. The amino group in the resin does not react preferably with the diamine group in the coupling agent.

Fig. 8. TGA thermograms of the glass/ Nylon 6 composites used in the work.

Fig. 9. Proposed reaction schemes between the different organo-functional groups in the silane coupling agents and the amino groups in the Nylon 6 resin.

CONCLUSION

The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of glass fiber/Nylon 6 composites sized with silane coupling agents used in the work are significantly

improved in comparison with the composite sized commercially. A silane coupling agent (Z-6076) with chloropropyl organofunctional groups shows the highest interfacial properties, followed by the Z-6030 with methacrylate group and the Z-6040 with epoxide group. The Z-6020 with diamine group exhibits the lowest values of IFSS and ILSS. The dynamic mechanical properties, the SEM observations of the fracture surfaces, and the thermal stability also support the interfacial results. Combining all the results, the fiber-matrix interfacial characteristics obtained from both microscopic (single fiber microbonding test, microscopy) and macroscopic (short-beam shear test, dynamic mechanical analysis) approaches agree well each other. However, it has been found that use of the Z-6040 is not good as much as others to make a glass/Nylon 6 composite, leading to poor wettability and resin impregnation during the composite fabrication even though it enhances the IFSS in a single fiber microbonding test.

The improvement of the interfacial properties may be interpreted in terms of different chemical reactivity between organo-functional groups located at the end of silane coupling agents with the other end anchored at the glass fiber surface and the reactive amino end groups at the Nylon 6 resin. The possibility of the chemical bond formation between the silane coupling agent and the Nylon 6 increases with increasing the chemical reactivity in order of chloropropyl > methacrylate \approx epoxide > diamine organo-functional groups.

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